

Mitigation of obesity in Mexico: a shared responsibility between the agri-food industry and consumers.

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ABSTRACT

Obesity amongst the Mexican population has increased rapidly in the last 10 years, having an impact in public health. This study aims to assess the impact of agri-food production indicators such as accessibility, availability and affordability (A³) of food and their impact on consumers' behaviour to further understand the nutritional transition in Mexico. The paper presents findings from a systematic literature review and secondary data analysis, which suggests the agriculture sector has an important role in improving nutrition. Initial findings from the literature review revealed that this sector has been highly neglected in Mexico, and recent uncertainties such as the North America Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) have had an impact on nutrition inequalities. Such inequalities could be addressed with a better understanding of the factors influencing the A³ of food products throughout the supply chain. In addition, the findings demonstrate the potential of understanding behaviour as a way of expanding awareness of the internal/external drivers affecting obesity. The findings from the literature review and secondary data analysis will complement further research including a survey to identify obesity trends and factors influencing poor nutrition in Mexican households. Outputs from the research will be compiled to develop scenarios that will analyse future threats and opportunities associated with changing diets and nutritional values in Mexico to support effective decision-making.

Keywords: Obesity, agri-food production, nutrition, consumer behaviour.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last 20 years, Mexico has experienced an increase of 30% in the number of people aged 15-75 years that are overweight and obese (OECD, 2017). Consequently, there is a burden placed on the public health institution, to balance the need for medical treatment and the continuous rise of diseases associated with obesity and being overweight, including: Type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension and cardiovascular diseases. This has had a significant impact at a national level, where there are estimated losses related to premature death and work absenteeism of \$USD28.8 billion, which represents a 2.3% loss of the gross domestic product (GDP) (Fernandez *et al.*, 2017).

In the last decade, increased obesity's level has prevailed in men and has risen in women. Barquera (2013) examined the National Health and Nutrition Survey (ENSANUT 2012), using combined data on the number of people overweight and obese (OW+O), and found an increase of 8.7% in men and 35.9% in women from 1988 to 2012.

In order to tackle obesity, which is a prevailing public health crisis, the Mexican government established a strategy with ten objectives to mitigate obesity (Barquera *et al.* 2013). Among them are increasing physical activity, promotion of good eating habits and a tax on sugar products. However, these targets have

proved challenging for the Mexican population. Findings from the Module of Sports Practice and Physical Exercise (MOPRADEF, 2017) showed that 58.2% of the population above age 18 years is currently inactive, and they prefer food with a lower nutritional value, which is a possible cause of increasing levels of obesity in this age group (Walls *et al.*, 2011). Other studies have reviewed the impact of taxes imposed on food and beverages with high contents of sugar and found a significant decrease in purchases among low and medium income household. However, the real impact is still unknown (Batis *et al.*, 2016) and further long-term research findings of the taxes' impact are required (Colchero *et al.*, 2016).

Good nutrition can be more effectively promoted through an integrated sectoral approach, that considers: availability, accessibility and affordability (A³) of nutritional food (e.g. fruits and vegetables); reducing nutrition inequalities among different socio-economic groups; and providing higher nutritional value products to people that could nudge healthier attitudes and behaviours (Gillespie and van den Bold, 2017). Many authors have noted the potential of the agri-food production system to improve consumer's eating habits (Arsenault *et al.*, 2015; Hawkes *et al.*, 2016; Schwab, 2017). Gillespie and van den Bold (2017) recommended establishing indicators that could link the agri-food system, and consumer attitudes and

behaviour related to nutrition and health, in order to optimize agriculture production, market and trade. However, there is very little literature published on the influence of agri-food production on consumers' behaviour. Thus, this study aims to identify indicators of the relationship between agriculture production (i.e. A³) and consumer's behaviour to further understand the underlying drivers of obesity in Mexico.

This paper presents findings from a systematic literature review and secondary data analysis, examining the influence of the agri-food production on consumer's behaviour through a STEEPLE framework (Social, Technology, Environment, Economic, Politics, Legal and Ethics) to further understand how the current system related to the A³ factors can impact nutrition.

2. Methodology

This paper is based on an analysis of literature and secondary data analysis, using a STEEPLE framework to identify the multiple factors that influence consumers' behaviour and nutrition in the Mexican population.

The literature review involved carrying out a systematic search of the academic databases (e.g. Scopus, Google Scholar, Web of Science) to identify the current nutritional issues in Mexico related to the incidence of obesity and being overweight in order to deepen understanding of the relationship and identify the possible associations between nutrition and agri-food production. Selected keywords for the search included Nutrition, Food Security, Diet-related non-communicable chronic diseases (NCCD's), Mexican Agri-food Production System, Consumer Behaviour, Nutrition Economics, Environment, and Nutrition inequalities. The overall number of papers found was 340, of which 95 were considered useful sources for this research project.

In addition to the literature review, secondary data was obtained from the Mexican Agriculture Secretariat (SAGARPA, 2016) and the Federal Prosecutor for the Consumer (PROFECO, 2017). Data obtained was gathered associating availability with factors of supply and trade by adding to the production the imports and subtracting the exports. Affordability was associated with the average price. Finally, the accessibility was associated with the domestic consumption. The data was analysed to explore the links/connection between agri-food production and the A³ factors with consumer behaviour and its impact to diet and nutrition.

3. Findings and Discussion: literature review

The results of the literature review are summarized to identify key associations between agri-food production

and consumer's behaviour in relation to the A³ factors using the STEEPLE framework:

3.1 Social

Unemployment within the agriculture sector in the 90's brought the need to migrate from rural to urban zones and/or to the US (UNCTAD, 2013). These demographic changes contributed to a Nutritional Transition, which impacted on eating/drinking behaviour amongst the Mexican population (Popkin, 2002; Hawkes, 2006). The new food patterns decreased the quality and quantity of diets (Swindale and Bilinsky, 2006). The nutrition transition increased the demand for more dense and nutrient-poor diets, with similar trends observed in both developed and developing countries (Aggarwal et al., 2011). In addition, it reduced the demand for whole grains, legumes, fruits and vegetables (Popkin, 2002; Rivera et al., 2004).

Mexico's inability to maintain agricultural production levels, increased demand for convenient and industrialized processed meals, especially from external food companies through foreign direct investments (FDI) (Hawkes, 2005; Pitt *et al.*, 2017). The result was higher accessibility to low nutritional value products (Adam Drewnowski and Barry M. Popkin, 1997; Maestre *et.*, al 2017).

Demographic changes in Mexico also led to a growth in the population and an increase of sedentary lifestyles (Jones *et al.*, 2003). This had impacts on mobility, where there was a tendency to replace walking/cycling practices with the use of public transportation/car for mobility. Therefore, an obesogenic environment was triggered because of changes in the social, cultural and political aspects in Mexico (Jones *et al.*, 2003).

3.2 Technology

The issues related to safety-trade has been an important weakness within the Mexican agri-production system (UNCTAD, 2013; Mora O, 2016). The need to improve agriculture productivity along with economic, health, nutrition and sustainability is imperative. Inherently this requires government investment in technological innovation to ensure water and food safety, good hygiene and environmental standards; and higher nutritional values across the population. By doing so, it could improve the elements of availability and accessibility linked to the increase in productivity simultaneously with the quality and safety of food products, and increase labour opportunities (Alston, *et.*, al 2009). Resulting in establishing an economic empowerment and gender equality (Ruel *et.*, al 2018) which will have a direct influence on the affordability

of food. Sustainable farming practice and technological innovations could improve agri-production systems and farm management practices (UNCTAD, 2013). Those improvements could increase the accessibility of agriculture products and subsequently its affordability (Lang and Barling, 2013). There is, however, a need for strong nutritional knowledge through orientation programs and effective access to technology through apps and programs that will deliver a basic understanding of what is a healthy diet.

3.3 Environment

The lack of technology and distribution systems of the neglected agriculture systems have had an important environmental impact related to food loss and waste. In a recent food loss and waste report, Gutiérrez (2017) assessed 79 products of the Mexican diet and found that more than 20.4 million tons of food were wasted annually. The CO² generated from the food waste was calculated and showed an equivalent level of emissions from approximately 15 million cars (Gutiérrez, 2017). In addition, food waste and overconsumption in households, contributed to an increased ecological footprint as showed in the Human Development Index (Heller and Keoleian, 2003; Moran et al. 2008; Khan et al., 2009; Heller, Keoleian and Willett, 2013). These environmental issues affect all A³ factors, resulting in the production of lower nutritional value products, which could negatively impact on nutrition and habits.

3.4 Economic

Imprecise policies between 1993 till 2010 within the agriculture sector caused a dropped in the employment levels from 8 to 5.8 million, which affected sector's productivity (UNCTAD, 2013). The need to import more food became the end of food sovereignty for the Mexican agriculture system. The commercial free-trade, mainly in the agriculture sector, brought negative balance for Mexican economy (Popkin 2001; Market Intelligence Latin America, 2014), increasing inflation and prices volatility (Oner, 2012). The new food prices benefited the affordability of products with long shelf-life due to their high conservative contents such as sugar, salt and saturated fats. Whereas 'short-life' products such as fresh fruits and vegetable prices constantly increased (Keller et al. 1997; Hawkes, 2006; Kant and Graubard, 2007; Maillot et al. 2007; Monsivais and Drewnowski, 2009; Bernstein et al. 2010; Stuckler and Nestle, 2012). This economic imbalance drove consumers to an 'addictive' palatable and 'poorer' nutritional choices (Darmon and Drewnowski, 2015).

3.5 Politics

The commercial free-trade agreement brought inequality and rising challenges to Mexican farmers, which meant that not all could cope with these changes and brought their businesses to extinction (Hawkes, 2006; Popkin, 2010; UNCTAD, 2013). One main reason was the new developed US policies that came along with the agreement, in which they were able to subsidy most of their local farmers, increasing the productivity gap between both countries (Wise and Development, 2010; UNCTAD, 2013; Friel and Ford, 2015). As a consequence, this impacted the public health sector (IFPRI, 2012). Policies failed to prioritize high quality and nutritional value to people's basic food baskets (UNCTAD, 2013). A clear example was the 'imminent' food businesses inequality, due to a high political support to FDI as a 'partial economic growth strategy' with their success in sales of unhealthy high-calorie food products (Hawkes, 2005). One main example of this are refreshment companies, with policies that allowed them easy and disproportionate access to natural resources like pure water. This has been done without any consideration to areas of the country with limited access to water, like the state of Chiapas (Albert *et al.*, 2014). This is a clear example of how the government policies have impacted on the availability of, and access to, low nutritional value products. In addition, these policies have had contributed to the current economic burden within the public health sector. Such as the epidemiological emergency type 2 diabetes and obesity. More research should focus on delivering the real 'numbers' between the 'gains' of supporting FDI and the economic waste for medical treatment associated with obesity and overweight. Decision-making needs to consider elements stated in the FAO's (2016) food security definition, of equality by delivering the power of purchase to products with a high nutritional value. To do so, Mexico requires in-depth studies of the current policies, prioritising nutrition equality and focusing on increasing the domestic food production as part of the country's growth plan. In other words, increase food sovereignty and sustainability.

3.6 Legal

Several strategic objectives were set by the Mexican government to mitigate the obesity and overweight crisis (Barquera et al, 2013). Among those objectives was the nutrition labelling with the purpose of bringing to the general public, the ability to be informed (Barquera et al. 2013). However, Stern (2013) showed that labelling such as the Guideline Daily Allowance (GDA) failed to communicate and increased confusion amongst the population regarding the nutritional

properties of food products. This situation delivered a wider gap between the food industry and consumers (FSA, 2016; De la Cruz-Góngora *et al.*, 2017). The outcome, therefore, is completely opposite of what the strategic objectives had aimed to achieve; including reducing consumer possibilities and power to make healthier informed decisions, and limiting the A³ aspects to higher nutritional value products due to the lack of unawareness. Therefore, new policies need to be put in place to deliver strategic objectives that could be understood by the general population. For example, if there is a limitation in terms of literacy and awareness, new regulations should consider these aspects. In addition, legislation set needs to prioritize all social levels to promote nutrition information effectively across all socio-economic groups.

3.7 Ethics

Ethical standards promote values which are essential within policies and regulations. To achieve them, there should be a priority for collaborative work, considering equality, trust and accountability. As reviewed in the different STEEPLE sections, nutrition equality should be instrumental in the mitigation of obesity and overweight people, especially in developing countries. In addition, regulation should avoid favouritisms within the food industry (Mody, 2002; Hawkes, 2005) and procure healthy and sustainable products. There should also be promotion of local consumption through A³. This could bring nutritional equality and economic balance, a promotion and encouragement of food sovereignty and sustainability.

4. Findings and Discussion: secondary data analysis

Findings from an analysis of the agri-food system, assessing the A³ revealed a gap between the availability of agri-food products, specifically vegetables and the domestic consumption. As shown in **Table 1**, this gap is present specifically in broccoli production with a total available of 8%, whereas the domestic demand of broccoli reaches 15%. This could be directly associated with the high export of broccoli (92%) from Mexico to the US (Hayley and Henrich, 2005), driven by an escalating consumption from the US population (1.14 kg annual per capita) compared to Mexican population (0.5 kg annual per capita) (USDA 2018; SAGARPA 2016). From a Mexican nutritional perspective, the consumption of cereal groups such as corn (100%) and wheat (69%) is higher compared to vegetable groups such as cucumber (18%) and broccoli (15%). Although the difference between the global prices and Mexican prices showed a negative balance for corn (-0.13), there was positive economic gain with broccoli (+0.56) and

cucumber (+0.29). Therefore, there could be a gap between the A³ of agri-food production and consumer behaviour.

Ramirez *et al.* (2006) investigated consumption patterns at a regional level and found a difference between the indigenous and non-indigenous population, which main difference between both groups would be living in urban areas or isolated rural areas. Findings showed that the low consumption of fruits and vegetables between the two groups would not necessarily be linked to a problem with the A³, rather this suggests a low demand for fruits and vegetables from both groups. Results could be associated with a hedonistic attitude, linked to consumer attitudes and behaviour. However, further study is needed for more conclusive results.

Table 1. Percentages and comparison of the A3 of selected food products from the Mexican Agri-food system.

Product	Production (tonnes)	Import (tonnes)	Export (tonnes)	% Export of what is total available (Production plus)	% Total availability (TA%)	% Domestic consumption (DC%) from the (TA%)-Accessibility	Difference between the (DC%) and the (TA%)-Accessibility	Average global price (USD)	Average price in Mexico (USD)	Diff. between the Global and Mexican average price-
Wheat	4,182,848	4,182,848	909,195	11%	89%	69%	+20%	USD \$0.54	USD \$0.54	0
Corn	24,694,046	11,974,519	730,067	2%	98%	100%	-2%	USD \$0.52	USD \$0.65	-0.13
Cucumber	817,800	0	676,897	83%	17%	18%	-1%	USD \$0.90	USD \$0.61	+0.29
Broccoli	415,812	3,794	386,493	92%	8%	15%	-7%	USD \$1.74	USD \$1.18	+0.56
Chickpeas	137,809	205	132,559	96%	4%	0.45%	+3.55%	USD \$1.51	USD \$1.75	-0.24

4. Conclusions and further work

From the literature review and secondary analysis findings, we conclude that by assessing the agri-food production and the A³ aspects, it could deliver important data for understanding current nutritional issues and the importance to relate it with consumer behaviour. In addition, findings helped to developed two hypotheses: 1) Current A³ of Mexican agri-food production system act as the main driver in the current eating behaviours of Mexican households' impacting

their nutrition; 2) There is a value action gap within Mexicans' eating behaviours, which is considered one main driver for obesity. These hypotheses are derived from the understanding that nutritional issues in Mexico should be assessed using a multidisciplinary approach to determine how the agri-food production system in Mexico impacts on behaviours, health and nutrition.

Further work will include a survey of consumers' eating behaviours associated with the A³, health status and nutritional knowledge in Mexican households. Furthermore, the development of scenarios planning to explore future threats and opportunities of the nutrition transition within the Mexican population to inform decision-making.

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